

DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL SELF-EDUCATION COMPETENCE OF FUTURE SPECIALISTS WITH MEDICAL EDUCATION

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At the present stage of society development, the preparation of competitive specialists ready for professional growth and self-education should be considered an important task of education. Self-education is one of the priority directions in education and it is especially noticeable in the period of professional formation. It is obvious that professional training of future staff of medical specialists should not only provide a certain level of knowledge, skills and abilities, but also develop the ability to self-education.

Key words: *competence, self-education, Internet, multimedia.*

На современном этапе развития общества важной задачей образования следует считать подготовку конкурентоспособных специалистов, готовых к профессиональному росту и самообразованию. Самообразование является одним из приоритетных направлений в образовании, и это особенно заметно в период профессионального становления. Очевидно, что профессиональная подготовка будущих кадров медицинских специалистов должна не только обеспечивать определенный уровень знаний, умений и навыков, но и развивать способность к самообразованию.

Ключевые слова: *компетентность, самообразование, Интернет, мультимедиа.*

A modern person should constantly improve his knowledge and skills, engage in self-education, have a multifaceted interest. The problem of self-education of a modern person has become especially urgent in the conditions of information society, where access to information and ability to work with it are key. Information society is characterized as a society of knowledge, where the process of transformation of

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information into knowledge plays a special role. Therefore, modern conditions require a person to constantly improve knowledge. Knowledge can be obtained in different ways. Today, a huge range of professional development services is offered. Therefore, the most effective way to improve skills is self-education. Constant self-education is the defining activity of life of a modern person, which will help to keep up with the "train of modernity". The most characteristic feature of professional activity is its mobility associated with changes in information resources and technologies, and we clearly realize that the former professional skills are quickly becoming obsolete, other forms and methods of work, theoretical knowledge of related sciences and much more are required. In order to keep up with these processes, it becomes necessary for a person to constantly learn. It is the modern person who should be close to the motto "Education for life. Education through life!", which is interpreted as an active process of acquiring new knowledge throughout the entire professional life. A person who is professionally orientated and willing to improve and learn is bound to achieve good results and a certain mastery. For this purpose, three main tasks must be realized and solved:

- to take into account the changes in the professional environment under the influence of informatization processes, socio-economic reforms;
- to constantly work on improving one's professional skills;
- to update knowledge and skills that provide him/her with a good creative form, the ability to actively assimilate modern achievements and experimental search;
- to seek ways and actively use methods of self-education, self-development and self-improvement.

Self-education, independent education, acquisition of systematic knowledge in any field of science, technology, culture, political life, etc., assuming direct personal interest of the student in an organic combination with the independence of study of the material. At the same time, self-education is a means of self-education, as it contributes to the development of purposefulness, perseverance in achieving the goal, internal organization, diligence and other moral qualities. In a broad sense, self-education is understood as all types of knowledge acquisition related to the independent work of the learner on the studied material. The main form of self-education is the study of scientific, popular science, educational, artistic and other literature, press. Self-education also includes the possibility of using various auxiliary means: listening to lectures, reports, concerts, consultations of specialists, watching plays, films, TV

programmer, visiting museums, exhibitions, galleries, various types of practical activities - experiments, experiments, modelling, etc. Self-education is a form of education in which a person teaches and educates himself/herself.

Based on the existing research on this problem, the term self-educational competence should be understood as a set of interrelated personal qualities, knowledge, skills, abilities, ways of activity, abilities, which determine the effectiveness of self-education. An important self-educational competence is an activity skill, including a skill, as mastering a competence means the ability to apply the available knowledge and experience in a particular situation and the ability to replenish the missing knowledge or acquire the necessary skills if necessary. This means that one of the main points is to create a basis for the emergence of the need for self-educational competence.

Formation of the need for self-educational competence can be carried out only directly in students' independent work. The use of Internet - resources for preparing reports, messages, participation in projects, e-mail correspondence, creating their own websites, communicating to exchange experience, as well as the possibility of distance learning via the Internet. The use of computer programs is simple, does not require high costs and serious training in terms of computer literacy and creates favorable conditions for the formation of self-educational competence. Given that the educational programmer of the third generation in the study of the professional module "Performing work in the profession of histology" includes an even greater amount of independent training of students, as well as the importance of the role of self-education of future medical personnel.

The competence of professional self-education is the ability to organize their own systematic educational activity and direct it to achieve the satisfaction of professional needs and improve professional qualification. The competence of professional self-education consists of a number of components:

- motivational and personal, reflecting the characteristic of attunement to professional self-education, awareness of personal and social significance of continuing education and their future profession, the presence of such personal qualities as independence, purposefulness, perseverance, activity, will;
- cognitive, consisting of knowledge relevant at the moment (knowledge of different ways of activity and types of information, knowledge of the laws of

communication, knowledge of the process of managing one's own activity, its methods and forms);

- informational and communicative - skills of independent work with information, possession of its various types and sources, information technologies; skills to find, process and use information to solve standard and non-standard professional tasks; culture of its perception and assimilation; ability of critical judgement in relation to information;

- activity - consisting of the ability to organize one's own activity, choose typical methods and ways of performing educational and professional tasks, evaluate their efficiency and quality;

- managerial-regulative, consisting of the skills that provide independent goal-setting, planning, organization, control, analysis, reflection, self-assessment, correction of students' own learning activities, the ability to manage their own behavior.

The main purpose of the adaptation stage is the actualization of motives and search for meaning in self-educational activity. The formation of experience of self-educational activity begins with the simplest trials of independent goal-setting and realization of educational intentions, which then grow into a specialist's own self-educational system. The following criteria for achieving the goal are defined: the degree of adequate assessment of students' achievements in setting increasingly complex tasks; awareness of the value and meaning of self-educational activity in relation to their personal and professional growth; possession of the experience of self-education (development of cognitive, general and organizational skills of self-educational activity).

At the first stage - analysis of psychological and pedagogical, methodological literature, dissertation works on the research problem; study of existing technologies of self-education, research of the problem in the theory and practice of medical education; definition of theoretical and methodological bases of building a system of formation of competences of professional self-education of medical students; specification of the purpose, object, subject, tasks, methods, content of the research; drawing up a plan of experimental and research work, development of the concepts of professional self-education, development of educational and methodological materials, development of mechanisms of diagnostics of the level of formation of competences of professional self-education of students.

At the second stage - development of the system of formation of competences of professional self-education of students, design of the process of student training aimed at the formation of competences of professional self-education, development of educational and methodical materials, mechanisms of diagnostics of the level of competence formation; analysis of the selected methods; carrying out of trial classes; verification and clarification of scientific and methodical conclusions.

At the third stage - processing, verification, analysis and systematization of the obtained data in order to determine the effectiveness of the proposed system of formation of competences of professional self-education, as well as generalization of the obtained results; development of scientific, methodological and practical recommendations to teachers and students on the formation of competences of professional self-education; implementation of the research results in the practice of the medical institute. Taking into account the criteria, three levels of development of self-educational competence were identified.

Low level - a future specialist is engaged in self-education, but not systematically. Motives of avoiding troubles, fear of showing low results prevail.

Average level - a future specialist devotes a lot of time to self-education, but there is no system in work. Cognitive motives prevail, manifested in the interest in the results of activity, motives of competitiveness.

High level - the future specialist is constantly engaged in self-education, and a clear system in work allows to achieve high results. Internal motives of enthusiasm for the process of self-education, self-esteem prevail, manifested in the desire to set increasingly difficult goals. In accordance with the level characteristics we have identified, each student is selected an individual programmer.

In its pedagogical activity it is important to solve the following tasks: the development of skills and skills of independent work; increasing the level of self-awareness of students; the formation of value attitude to the profession, as well as the development of students' ability to reflect on their life, student experience; the student's vision of the prospects of self-development, revealing the creative potential of the personality.

Based on the above mentioned, for the formation of competence of professional self-education of future specialists with medical education it is necessary: selection of individual programmer for each student; use of active teaching methods (trainings,

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problem solving, interactive learning, use of Internet resources, etc.); involvement of students in research work on the subject of classes and current problems of health care.

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